

Radical Copolymerization of 2-Vinylpyridine with Ethylmethacrylate and Butylmethacrylate in Dimethylformamide

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The radical copolymerization of 2-vinylpyridine (2VP) with ethyl methacrylate (EMA) and butyl methacrylate (BMA) has been investigated in dimethyl formamide (DMF) at 95° using AIBN as an initiator. The reactivity ratios of these comonomeric pairs, (2VP-EMA) and (2VP-BMA) have been determined by the application of Finemann-Ross and Kelen-Tudos methods. The copolymers have been characterised by ir and elemental analysis. The mean sequence lengths (\bar{n}) and probabilities (P) in the formation of various structural units have been evaluated for these copolymers.

ALFREY *et al.*¹ studied the free radical copolymerization of 2-vinylpyridine (2VP) with methacrylate and methyl methacrylate and determined reactivity ratios of the copolymer systems. Reactivity ratios of 2VP with various acrylates were also determined by various workers². However, studies on copolymerization of 2VP with ethyl methacrylate (EMA) and butyl methacrylate (BMA) are not reported. We report here the reactivity ratios, sequence length distribution and distribution probabilities of 2VP copolymers.

Experimental

EMA and BMA (Fluka) was freed from inhibitor by washing with 5% NaOH and water and dried over calcium chloride and distilled twice under reduced pressure, 2VP³ (Fluka) and DMF (AnalaR) were purified. The initiator azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) was crystallised from methanol.

Procedure: Copolymerization reactions were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere with AIBN at varying feed ratios of 2VP-EMA and 2VP-BMA in DMF at 95°. The total monomers concentration was maintained at 1.699 mol dm⁻³ for 2VP-EMA system and 1.5 mol dm⁻³ for 2VP-BMA system, while the ratios 2VP-EMA and 2VP-BMA were varied. The copolymers prepared at low conversions were isolated by precipitation of the reaction mixtures with distilled water at low temperature, purified by reprecipitation from acetone-water, filtered and dried under reduced pressure at room temperature.

Polymer characterisation: The copolymers were characterised by ir and elemental analysis. The ir spectra (KBr) were obtained using a Perkin-Elmer 125 spectrophotometer. The copolymer compositions were determined on the basis of the nitrogen content using a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyser.

The copolymer composition were ascertained from the 2VP content in the copolymers. The r values for the 2VP-EMA and 2VP-BMA systems were estimated by Fineman-Ross⁴ (F-R) equation (1) and Kelen-Tudos⁴ (K-T) equation (2),

$$F(f-1)/f = r_1 F^2 / f - r_2 \quad (1)$$

$$\eta = (r_1 + r_2 / 2) \xi - r_2 / \alpha \quad (2)$$

where the terms and symbols have usual significance⁶. From the plot of η vs ξ intercept of $\xi=1$ gives r_1 and intercept at $\xi=0$ gives r_2/α .

The mean sequence-lengths (\bar{n}_1 and \bar{n}_2) and distribution probabilities were calculated using equation suggested by Ekpenyong⁷.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra of the copolymers show a peak at 1720 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of ester carbonyl groups for EMA or BMA and also a broad peak at 3420 cm⁻¹ which is an overtone of C=O stretching frequency. The peaks at 3000, 1600-1430 and 740 cm⁻¹ for aromatic C-H stretch, C-C, C-N ring stretching (skeletal bands) and C-H out-of-plane bending respectively indicate the presence of pyridine group for 2VP.

Reactivity ratios: From the composition of the copolymers the reactivity ratios of 2VP-EMA and 2VP-BMA systems were evaluated by F-R and K-T methods. Monomer feeds and copolymer compositions for both the copolymer systems are given in Table I.

The values of reactivity ratios so determined were r_1 (2VP) = 0.55 ± 0.01, r_2 (EMA) = 0.71 ± 0.02 by the both F-R and K-T (Fig. 1) methods for 2VP-EMA copolymer system. In this case, while EMA can add on to 2VP, 2VP can add on to EMA at the same time. The preference for one of these two will

TABLE 1—MONOMER FEEDS AND COPOLYMER COMPOSITION FOR 2VP-EMA AND 2VP-BMA COPOLYMER SYSTEMS IN MOLE FRACTIONS

Sl. no.	2VP-EMA System					2VP-BMA System				
	Feed composition		N%	Copolymer composition		Feed composition		N%	Copolymer composition	
	2VP(M ₁)	EMA(M ₂)		2VP(m ₁)	EMA(m ₂)	2VP(M ₁)	BMA(M ₂)		2VP(m ₁)	BMA(m ₂)
1.	0.410	0.590	5.14	0.405	0.595	0.200	0.800	4.59	0.416	0.594
2.	0.469	0.531	5.75	0.452	0.548	0.266	0.734	4.90	0.440	0.560
3.	0.519	0.481	6.36	0.498	0.502	0.333	0.667	5.96	0.523	0.477
4.	0.587	0.413	6.99	0.545	0.455	0.400	0.600	6.42	0.557	0.443
5.	0.646	0.354	7.60	0.590	0.410	0.466	0.534	6.96	0.587	0.413

depend on the actual values of r_1 and r_2 and also on the monomer feed ratios. For this system r_2 is greater than r_1 , which indicates that the copolymer formed will be richer in EMA. For 2VP-BMA copolymer system the reactivity ratios were r_1 (2VP) = 0.84 ± 0.03 , r_2 (BMA) = 0.170 ± 0.04 and $r_1 = 0.82 \pm 0.04$, $r_2 = 1.170 \pm 0.05$ according to F-R and K-T (Fig. 2) methods respectively. In this case, while BMA can add on to 2VP, 2VP can add on to BMA at the same time. For this system r_1 is greater than r_2 which indicates that the copolymer formed will be richer in 2VP.

Fig. 1. Kelen-Tudos plots for determination of reactivity ratios of (Δ) 2VP/BMA and (○) 2VP/EMA systems.

Fig. 2. Copolymerization diagram, the monomer F_1 and copolymer f_1 compositions are expressed as molar ratios with respect to 2VP: (○) 2VP-EMA and (Δ) 2VP-BMA systems.

To ascertain normal copolymer kinetic behaviour the plot of f_1 vs F_1 (Fig. 2) was drawn, in which f_1 is the mole fraction of 2VP in 2VP-EMA and 2VP-BMA systems, F_1 is that of feed (Table 1). The shape of the curves indicates that the azeotropic compositions of the copolymer systems and the distribution of monomeric units are random and in no case a homopolymer formation is expected. The azeotropic compositions for the two systems are also determined by equation⁸ (3).

$$N_1 = (1 - r_2) / (2 - r_1 - r_2) \tag{3}$$

The values for 2VP-EMA and 2VP-BMA copolymers are 0.38 and 0.825 respectively. The value of 0.38 (from equation 3 and Fig. 2) for 2VP-EMA copolymer suggests that the copolymer will be richer in 2VP below this point, but richer in EMA above it. Similarly, for 2VP-BMA copolymer the value of 0.825 (from equation 3 and Fig. 2) indicates that the copolymer is richer in 2VP upto this point, but richer in BMA above it. In both the copolymers the monomers were arranged in a random sequence.

Sequence length distribution: Table 2 shows the mean sequence lengths \bar{n}_1 and \bar{n}_2 for the formation of M_1 and M_2 units calculated using equations

TABLE 2—MEAN SEQUENCE LENGTH DISTRIBUTION OF THE COPOLYMERIZATION OF 2VP-EMA AND 2VP-BMA

Sl. no.	[M ₁] mol %	\bar{n}_1	\bar{n}_2	\bar{n}_1/\bar{n}_2	$\bar{n}_1 : \bar{n}_2$	Distribution*
2VP-EMA :						
1.	41.0	1.38	2.025	0.681	1 : 2	...1221...
2.	46.9	1.48	1.806	0.819	1 : 2	—
3.	51.9	1.61	1.636	0.984	2 : 2	...112211...
4.	58.7	1.78	1.500	1.186	2 : 2	—
5.	64.6	2.00	1.389	1.439	2 : 1	...11211...
2VP-BMA :						
6.	20.0	1.205	1.684	0.715	1 : 2	...1121...
7.	26.0	1.298	1.470	0.883	1 : 2	—
8.	33.3	1.410	1.342	1.051	1 : 1	...1212...
9.	40.0	1.546	1.356	1.231	2 : 1	—
10.	46.6	1.717	1.195	1.437	2 : 1	...11211...

*Only a few cases are illustrated.

suggested by Ekpenyong⁷. For example, at 41% M₁ (2VP) (59% M₂ (EMA)) in the monomer mixture each copolymer segment with M₂ units in 2VP-EMA polymerization was approximately double than its adjoining segment with M₁ units. The sequence may be expressed as —1221. For the 2VP-BMA copolymer, at 20% M₁ (2VP), (80% M₂ (BMA)) in the monomer mixture each copolymer segment with M₂ units was approximately double than its adjoining segment with M₁ units. In the both

copolymers it constitutes the range in which a sizeable amount of both the monomers is incorporated into the copolymers. The ratios of the mean sequence lengths \bar{n}_1/\bar{n}_2 , which theoretically correspond to the ratio dm_1/dm_2 ; dm_1 and dm_2 are the corresponding composition of M₁ and M₂ in the copolymer for each monomer mixture defined.

The microstructure of a copolymer is defined by the distribution of the various lengths of the M₁ and M₂ sequences, that is, the sequences-length distributions. The probabilities or mole fractions (N_1)_x and (N_2)_x of forming M₁ and M₂ sequence of length x are given by equations⁹,

$$(N_1)_x = P_{11}^{x-1} P_{12} \quad (4)$$

$$(N_2)_x = P_{22}^{x-1} P_{21} \quad (5)$$

where, $P_{11} = \frac{r_1[M_1]}{r_1[M_1] + [M_2]}$, $P_{12} = \frac{[M_2]}{r_1[M_1] + [M_2]}$

$$P_{22} = \frac{r_2[M_2]}{r_2[M_2] + [M_1]}, P_{21} = \frac{[M_1]}{r_2[M_2] + [M_1]}$$

equations (4 and 5) allow one to calculate the mole fractions of different lengths of M₁ and M₂ sequences. Figs. 3a and 3b show the sequence-length distribution for 2VP-EMA copolymerization with $r_1=0.55$, $r_2=0.71$ for 1.004/0.695 and 0.6024/1.097 feed compositions respectively and Figs. 3c and 3d show the

Fig. 3. Sequence-length distributions for : (a) EMA in a 2VP-EMA copolymer ; feed composition 2VP/EMA=1.004/0.695 ; (b) EMA in a 2VP-EMA copolymer ; feed composition 2VP/EMA=0.6024/1.097 ; (c) BMA in a 2VP-BMA copolymer ; feed composition 2VP/BMA=0.30/1.20 ; (d) BMA in a 2VP-BMA copolymer ; feed composition 2VP/BMA=0.70/0.80.

TABLE 3—DISTRIBUTION PROBABILITIES (P) FOR THE COPOLYMERIZATION OF 2VP-EMA AND BMA

Sl. no.	Concentration		P_{11}	P_{111}	P_{1111}	P_{22}	P_{222}	P_{2222}
	$[M_1]$	$[M_2]$						
2VP-EMA :								
1.	1.004	0.695	0.443	0.247	0.109	0.329	0.221	0.073
2.	0.904	0.796	0.384	0.237	0.091	0.385	0.237	0.091
3.	0.803	0.890	0.332	0.222	0.073	0.440	0.246	0.108
4.	0.703	0.996	0.279	0.201	0.056	0.502	0.250	0.125
5.	0.602	1.097	0.232	0.178	0.041	0.564	0.246	0.138
2VP-BMA :								
6.	0.30	1.20	0.170	0.141	0.024	0.406	0.241	0.098
7.	0.40	1.10	0.229	0.176	0.040	0.320	0.218	0.070
8.	0.50	1.00	0.291	0.206	0.060	0.255	0.190	0.048
9.	0.60	0.90	0.353	0.228	0.081	0.204	0.162	0.033
10.	0.70	0.80	0.418	0.243	0.102	0.163	0.136	0.022

sequence length distribution for 2VP-BMA copolymerization with $r_1=0.82$, $r_2=171$ for 0.30/1.20 and 0.70/0.80 feed compositions respectively.

From Fig. 3a for 2VP-EMA system the most plentiful sequence is M_2 at 68% ; there are other sequence, 22% and 7% respectively, of diad, triad M_2 sequence and a smaller amount of tetrad sequence. For other feed composition (Fig. 3b) the most plentiful sequence is M_2 at 44% with 24.5, 14, 8 and 4% respectively of diad, triad, tetrad and pentad M_2 sequence. There are smaller amounts of longer sequences 2% and 1.5% of hexad and hepted M_2 sequences.

From the Fig. 3c and 3d for 2VP-BMA system, the only most plentiful sequence is M_1 at 60% and 84% for different feed compositions respectively, there are considerable amounts of diad, triad and tetrad M_1 sequency only possible, and no longer sequences are possible.

Table 3 lists the probabilities of the formation of structural units such as M_1M_1 , $M_1M_1M_1$, M_2M_2 and $M_2M_2M_2$ which were calculated from equations given by Ekpenyong⁷. For example, $[M_1]=1.004$, $[M_2]=0.6954$ for 2VP-EMA system, P_{11} (for M_1M_1 formation) is approximately 10% larger than P_{22} (M_2M_2 formation) in the copolymerization. But in the 2VP-BMA system for $[M_1]=0.7$, $[M_2]=0.8$, P_{11} is approximately three times larger P_{22} probabilities of formation of higher species (triplets, quarters etc.) show similar behaviour in the copolymerization. If P is expressed in percentage (here a crude approximation that takes into account only those species that makes a significant contribution) then, for example 2VP-EMA system, when $[M_1]=1.004$, $[M_2]=0.695$, P_{11} constitutes approximately 44%, whereas P_{22} accounts for 33% in the copolymer chain. For 2VP-BMA system, when $[M_1]=0.7$, $[M_2]=0.8$, P_{11} constitutes approximately 42%, whereas P_{22} accounts for only 16% in the copolymer chain.

These results demonstrate the great utility of the monomer pair reactivity ratios in that with known r -values a desired distribution by calculation can be predetermined and a copolymer of desired composition can be prepared.

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